

Synthesis and antimicrobial elucidation of [1,2,4]-triazole-3-thione derivatives

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Abstract : 4-Nitro benzoyl isothiocyanate (1) is prepared by a reaction of 4-nitro benzoyl chloride and ammonium isothiocyanate. Compound 1 reacts with phenyl hydrazine in the presence of acetone to form 5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3(2*H*)-thione (2). Compounds 2 on reaction with formaldehyde and different aromatic amines in 1,4-dioxane yielded 2-(substituted-amino)methyl-5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3(2*H*)-thione (3a-j) respectively. The synthesized compound 3a-j were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities and characterized by spectral techniques like IR and NMR.

Keywords : Acid chloride, aryl hydrazine, ammonium thiocyanate, 1,2,4-triazole-3-thione, Mannich reaction, mercapto-1,2,4-triazole.

Introduction

Triazoles have been reported to possess antimicrobial¹⁻⁵, antiinflammatory⁶⁻⁸, anticonvulsant⁹, diuretic¹⁰, antihypertensive¹¹, anti-HIV¹², antitubercular¹³ activities, etc.

In the synthesis of biologically active heterocyclic compounds, it was considered worthwhile to synthesize some more 1,2,4-triazoles and evaluate them antibacterial and antifungal activities. In the present article we describe the synthesis of various triazole derivatives. Consideration, 4-nitro benzoyl chloride and ammonium thiocyanate in dry acetone gave 4-nitro benzoyl isothiocyanate (1). The compound 1 on reaction with phenyl hydrazine produced 5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3(2*H*)-thione (2) respectively. Compound 2 contains one active hydrogen atom and therefore, Mannich reaction is suitable for further synthesis¹⁴. Compound 2 is reacted with formaldehyde and 4-chloro aniline in the presence of 1,4-dioxane, yielded Mannich base 2-((4-chlorophenylamino)methyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-(2*H*)-thione (3a) respectively. All the synthesized compounds were characterized by infrared and ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy. The compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity towards Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains data.

Biological activity :

Ten compounds of [1,2,4]-triazole-3-thione derivatives were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities. The antimicrobial activity was assayed by using the Broth Dilution Method^{15,16} by measuring the Minimal Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC) and Minimal Fungicidal Concentrations (MFC) in µg/ml. The antibacterial activity was carried out against *E. coli*, *P. auroginosa*, *S. aureus* and *S. pyogenus*. The standard drug used was Gentamycin. The antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, *A. niger* and *A. clavatus*, the standard antifungal Nystatin was used for a comparison of results and are presented in Table 2.

Experimental

TLC was used to monitor the reaction and to check the purity of the compounds synthesized and the compounds are purified by column chromatography using silica gel (60-120 mesh). The melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr disk) were recorded on FT-IR-thermonicolate IR-200 spectrometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker DRX 300 in CDCl₃ at 200 MHz using TMS as an internal standard.

Synthesis of 5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-[1,2,4]-triazole-3-thione (2) :

A solution of 4-nitro benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in

Table 1. Characterization of compounds 3a-j

Compd.	Ar	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Found (Calcd.) %		
					C	H	N
3a	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	54	180	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O ₂ S	57.62 (57.60)	3.70 (3.68)	15.97 (15.99)
3b	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	59	188	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O ₂ S	57.58 (57.60)	3.70 (3.68)	15.99 (15.99)
3c	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	63	208	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂ S	63.30 (63.29)	4.63 (4.59)	16.82 (16.78)
3d	3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	57	211	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂ S	63.32 (63.29)	4.62 (4.59)	16.82 (16.78)
3e	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	68	234	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂ S	63.30 (63.29)	4.60 (4.59)	16.82 (16.78)
3f	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	55	171	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S	56.22 (56.24)	3.62 (3.60)	18.78 (18.74)
3g	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	70	202	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S	56.23 (56.24)	3.62 (3.60)	18.77 (18.74)
3h	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	58	149	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S	56.23 (56.24)	3.61 (3.60)	18.74 (18.74)
3i	3-Cl-4-F-C ₆ H ₃	49	143	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ClFN ₅ O ₂ S	55.30 (55.33)	3.28 (3.32)	15.34 (15.36)
3j	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	53	192	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ BrN ₅ O ₂ S	52.31 (52.29)	3.35 (3.34)	14.50 (14.52)

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of compounds 3a-j

Compd.	Ar	Antibacterial activity is expressed in the form of Minimal Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC) in µg/mL				Antifungal activity is expressed in the form of Minimal Fungicidal Concentrations (MFC) in µg/mL		
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. clavatus</i>
		MTCC-	MTCC-	MTCC-	MTCC-	MTCC-	MTCC-	MTCC-
3a	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	443	1688	96	442	227	282	1323
3b	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	100	200	250	50	250	500	500
3c	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	50	200	25	1000	500	250	500
3d	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	100	50	500	500	> 1000	500	1000
3e	3-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	500	500	1000	1000	500	1000	1000
3e	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	250	500	500	1000	> 1000	1000	> 1000
3f	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	500	250	500	250	500	> 1000	1000
3g	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	100	50	50	500	500	250	> 1000
3h	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	200	200	250	500	> 1000	> 1000	500
3i	3-Cl-4-F-C ₆ H ₃	100	50	50	200	200	150	500
3j	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	25	250	250	1000	250	500	500

dry acetone (50 ml), ammonium thiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added with constant stirring at room temperature. Stirred reaction for half an hour. After the completion of reaction the formed precipitate of ammonium chloride was filtered and the filtrate containing 4-nitro benzoyl

isothiocyanate (1). The phenyl hydrazine (0.011 mol) was added in the filtrate, then the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 5 h, the resulting solid was filtered and washed with water and cold acetone to get compound 2. Yield 59%, m.p. 186 °C (Found : C, 56.30; H, 3.35; N,

where, Ar = Different aryl groups

Scheme 1

18.80. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{10}N_4O_2S$: C, 56.37; H, 3.38; N, 18.78%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}): 3450 (-NH stretching of secondary amine), 3040 (-CH stretching of aromatic ring), 1610 (-C=N stretching of triazole ring), 1520 (-N=O stretching of aromatic $-NO_2$ group), 1240 (-C=S stretching of triazole ring); 1H NMR: δ 2.1 (1H, s), 6.9 (1H, d), 7.3–7.4 (4H, m), 8.1–8.3 (4H, m).

2-[(4-Chlorophenylamine)-methyl]-5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-1,2-dihydro-[1,2,4]-triazole-3-thione (3a):

A mixture of compound 2a (0.01 mol), formaldehyde (0.01 mol) and 4-chloro aniline (0.01 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (50 ml) was stirred for 24 h. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was neutralized with the liquor ammonia solution then poured in water and in this mixture ethyl acetate was added for the extraction of the final compound 3a. Distilled out the solvent to get compound 3a, which was recrystallized from methanol, % yield of compound 3a was 54%, m.p. 180 °C (Found: C, 57.62; H, 3.70; N, 15.97. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{16}ClN_5O_2S$: C, 57.60; H, 3.68; N, 15.99%); IR (cm^{-1}): 3320 (-NH stretching of secondary amine), 3030 (-CH stretching of aromatic ring), 2870 (-CH stretching of $-CH_2$ group), 1620 (C=C- stretching of aromatic ring), 1520 (-N=O stretching of aromatic $-NO_2$ group), 1340 (C-N stretching of secondary amine), 1100 (-C-S stretching of thio ketone), 810 (-CH bending of *p*-substituted benzene ring), 760 (C-Cl stretching of aromatic Cl group); 1H NMR: δ 4.4 (2H, s), 6.1 (1H, s), 6.5 (2H, d), 6.9 (1H, t), 7.2–7.4 (7H, m), 8.1 (2H, d), 8.3 (2H, d).

Other compounds 3b-j were synthesized similarly from compound 2, characterization data are presented in Table 1.

Results and discussion

In antibacterial study the Minimal Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) indicates that the value of MBC 12.5, 25 and 50 show excellent, good and moderately active respectively. Antibacterial screening of above mentioned compounds indicated that compound 3b is moderately active and 3j is fairly active against *E. coli*. Compounds 3c, 3g and 3i are moderately active against *P. aeruginosa*. Compounds 3g and 3i are moderately active and 3b is fairly active against *S. aureus* and the compound 3a shows moderate activity against *S. pyogenes*.

The antifungal results that Minimal Fungicidal Concentration (MFC) 100, 150–200 and 250 indicate excellent, good and moderate active respectively. Antifungal activity results indicate that compounds 3a, 3i and 3j are moderately active against *C. albicans*. Compounds 3c, 3g and 3i are moderately active against *A. niger*.

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